

SIMULATION PROBABILITY OF CLEAN WATER AVAILABILITY IN ONE OF THE AREA OF DRINKING WATER COMPANIES IN BANDUNG CITY

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Abstract— Water is a basic necessity that is very important for human life. With the increase in the number of residents and institutions in an area, especially in the city of Bandung, the level of use of clean water has increased. While clean water has been difficult to obtain because many water sources have been contaminated by household and factory waste. Because of this to get clean water must go through a regional water company (PDAM). However, PDAM only have limited water deposits depending on the source of water obtained, for example water sources are obtained from rivers, lakes, reservoirs, springs, groundwater, etc. From water sources that are obtained by climate change and natural conditions that often change, the water sources that will be treated by the PDAM are reduced and more and more people are in need of water. For this reason, forecasting is needed about when the water in a PDAM runs out and must find or make new water sources so that clean water is always distributed to the population.

Keywords: clean water, water source.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is very necessary in human life both for it to be consumed and used for other purposes. The water consumption is used by a growing number of residents.

With the consumption of clean water which is always increasing, the production of clean water needs to be increased so that clean water is not used up and can always be distributed.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

There are several factors that affect water resources, namely water hydrologic cycle evapotranspiration process can be in the state in the equation (1) :

$$ET_o = c \times [w \times R_n + (1-w) \times f(u) \times (e_a - e_d)] \quad (1)$$

Where:

ET_o = References Evapotranspiration (mm/day)

w = heavy factor between temperature and sun radiation

R_n = sun radiation

$f(u)$ = a function of wind speed

$e_a - e_d$ = The difference between the pressure of saturated water

vapor at average air temperature with the average water vapor pressure in the air

c = replacement factor due to the weather conditions day and night

With the presence of evapotranspiration factors, PDAM's water resources lose about 20% of the total water each year.

And factors that greatly affect water resources are consumers of clean water, population (dom) and agency (non-dom)) So that the total loss of water per year can be expressed in the equation (2):

$$1 \text{ Year} = \sum \text{water supply} - ((20\% \times \sum \text{water supply}) + (\sum \text{dom} + \sum \text{nondom})) \quad (2)$$

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method applied is descriptive and quantitative analysis to make certain conclusions. By carrying out data collection in the form of many PDAM users, the amount of water availability every year, climate change in an area.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

With the increasing number of population and institutions, the amount of water used is increasing. The importance of adequate quantity of water for human health can be done in several ways such as the use of sufficient water for hand washing, hygiene, and bathing. Water is important enough for hydration and food preparation. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the standard of drinking water needs for each person is 20 L per person per day, so that the total water needs of 100 L of water per person per day are optimal to ensure that the water consumption and hygiene needs are fulfilled. so that the PDAM needs to make or search for new water resources so that water is always distributed.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This research is done by speed system so that it allows a lot of errors in the making. This research needs to add more ideas and research data to increase the accuracy of the estimates made.

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